

Supporting Information

An Organic Molecular Nanobarrel that Hosts and Solubilizes C₆₀

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Scheme S1. Synthetic route for $\text{C}_{60}@1$.

Figure S1. Structure of the different stoichiometric barrels [2+4], [3+6] and [4+8] by the dynamic self-assembly of the building blocks **2** and **3**. Molecular structures and energies computed at the GFN2-xTB-Chloroform level.

Figure S2. FTIR spectra of precursor **2** and barrel **1**.

Figure S3. VT-NMR spectrum of **1** ($1,1,2,2$ -tetrachloroethane- d_2 , 400 MHz). Asterisks indicate solvent residual peaks.

Figure S4. ^{13}C NMR spectra of precursor **2** and nanobarrel **1** in 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane-*d*₂.

Figure S5. Absorption (top) and emission (below) spectra of precursor **2** and barrel **1** in chloroform (10^{-5} M).

Figure S6. Absorption spectra of barrel **1** (10^{-5} M) after the gradual addition of C_{60} (10^{-5} M) in chloroform-toluene (9:1).

Figure S7. DOSY spectrum of **C₆₀@1** (1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane-*d*₂, 400 MHz, 298K). Asterisks indicate solvent residual peaks.

Figure S8. MALDI-TOF MS spectrum of $C_{60}@1$. In addition to the $[C_{60}@1+Ag]^+$ peak, a less intense peak corresponding to $[1+Ag]^+$ can be observed, illustrating that decomplexation can take place during ionization in the gas phase.

Figure S9. Absorption spectrum of the C₆₀, barrel 1 and C₆₀@1 complex (10⁻⁵ M, in all cases) in chloroform-toluene (9:1).

Table S1. Yield of barrel **1** under different conditions.

Solvent	Temperature	Catalyst	Time	Yield (%)
Chloroform	RT	TFA	5 days	84
Dichloromethane	RT	TFA	5 days	42
Tetrachloroethane	RT	TFA	5 days	36
Chloroform	RT	No catalyst	5 days	47
Chloroform	50 °C	TFA	5 days	30

Table S2. Reaction energies (GFN2-xTB in chloroform continuum). All energies are in Kcal/mol.

Barrel Stoichiometry	Total Energy	Normalization Factor	Normalization Energy
[2+4]	-26.7	2	-13.3
[3+6]	-92.1	3	-30.7
[4+8]	-113.5	4	-28.4

Table S3. Orbitals eigenvalues at the M06-2X-6-31G(d,p)-Chloroform level. All energies are in eV.

	LUMO+3	LUMO+2	LUMO+1	LUMO	HOMO	HOMO-1	HOMO-2	HOMO-3	HOMO-4	HOMO-5	Gap
C₆₀	-1.16	-2.53	-2.53	-2.53	-7.08	-7.08	-7.08	-7.08	-7.09	-8.58	4.55
1	-0.48	-0.93	-0.94	-0.95	-6.38	-6.39	-6.42	-7.18	-7.19	-7.20	5.43
C₆₀@1	-1.18	-2.47	-2.49	-2.49	-6.35	-6.36	-6.37	-6.89	-6.94	-6.95	3.86

General Methods.

Commercial chemicals and solvents were used as received.

Analytical thin layer chromatography (TLC) was carried out using aluminum sheets (20x20 cm) pre-coated with silica gel RP-18W 60 F254 from Merck.

Column chromatography was carried out using Silica gel 60 (40-60 μm) from Scharlab.

NMR spectra in solution were recorded on a Bruker Avance 400 MHz or 500 MHz spectrometer at 298 K using partially deuterated solvents as internal standards.

Matrix Assisted Laser Desorption Ionization (coupled to a Time-Of-Flight analyzer) experiments (MALDI-TOF) were recorded on Bruker REFLEX spectrometer in POLYMAT by Dra. Estíbaliz González de San Román Martín.

Absorption spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Lambda 950 spectrometer.

Fluorescence spectra were recorded on a LS55 Perkin-Elmer Fluorescence spectrometer.

Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectra were taken on a Bruker Optics ALPHA-E spectrometer with a universal Zn-Se ATR (attenuated total reflection) accessory in the 600–4000 cm^{-1} region or using a Diamond ATR (Golden Gate).

Absorption and fluorescence titrations were carried out simultaneously following a recent procedure used to study the complexation between cages and fullerenes.^[1] In a typical titration experiment, a fluorescence cuvette (1 cm) was filled with 3 mL of a solution of nanobarrel **1** (10^{-5} M) in a chloroform-toluene (9:1, spectroscopic grade) mixture. Then, a concentrated solution of C_{60} (10^{-3} M) in a chloroform-toluene (9:1, spectroscopic grade)

mixture was added in aliquots (3 μ L, 0.1 eq.). The UV-Vis absorption and fluorescence spectra were recorded after the addition of each aliquot. The binding constants were calculated from the peak at 416 nm of three different titrations using the modified Benesi-Hildebrand equation (see below) and Bindfit's Nelder-Mead method.^[2] The modified Benesi-Hildebrand equation is, $F_{\text{max}} / (F_{\text{max}} - F_x) = 1 + (1/K) (1/[M]n)$ where F_{max} and F_x are the emission intensities of nanobarrel **1** in the absence of C_{60} and at an intermediate concentrations of fullerene respectively, where K is the binding constant, M is the concentration of fullerene and, for this particular system, n is 1.

Computational Methods.

To explore the conformation space, 100 ps molecular dynamics trajectories in a solvent continuum computed with extended tight-binding (xTB) quantum chemistry methodologies were used.^[3] From these, 100 snapshots were periodically selected from each trajectory, optimized and energy ranked to be later refined with DFT. Final geometry optimizations were performed with Gaussian09 at the M06-2X-6-31G(d,p) level in chloroform.

Synthesis of 2.

4,5,9,10-tetrabromo-2,7-di-tert-butylpyrene^[41] (1.26 g, 2 mmol), 4-formyl phenylboronic acid (2.4 g, 16 mmol), K₂CO₃ (0.83 g, 6 mmol) and Pd(PPh₃)₄ (0.46 g, 0.4 mmol) were taken together in a 250 ml round-bottomed flask. The reaction mixture was kept under vacuum for 30 mins. In another flask, 54 ml of DMF and 18 ml of water were taken and bubbled with nitrogen for 15 mins. Thereafter, the reaction mixture flask was sealed using a rubber septum and a N₂ balloon was placed. Subsequently, the solvent was added to the reaction mixture in presence of the N₂ atmosphere. The reaction temperature was raised to 90 °C and the reaction was stirred for 18 h under the N₂ atmosphere. After being cooled to room temperature, the reaction mixture was extracted with chloroform, washed well with water. The organic phase was collected, dried with sodium sulphate and evaporated under reduced pressure. The solid residue was chromatographed on silica, eluting with chloroform, to afford the desired product **2** (0.29 g, 20%) as white powder.

¹H-NMR (1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane-*d*₂, 400 MHz, 298K) δ (ppm) : 10.02 (s, 4H), 7.88 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, 8H), 7.85 (s, 4H), 7.50 (d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, 8H), 1.24 (s, 18H).

¹³C-NMR (1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane-*d*₂, 125 MHz, 298K) δ (ppm) : 192.12, 149.35, 145.92, 136.79, 135.06, 131.83, 129.93, 129.38, 122.44, 122.22, 120.36, 35.30, 31.53

MS MALDI (*m/z*): 731.308. Calculated for [M+H]⁺ C₅₂H₄₃O₄: 731.315.

Figure S10. ^1H -NMR spectrum of **2** (1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane- d_2 , 400 MHz, 298K). Asterisks indicate solvent residual peaks.

Figure S11. ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of **2** (1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane- d_2 , 125 MHz, 298K). Asterisks indicate solvent residual peaks.

Synthesis of barrel 1.

Compound **2** (0.2 mmol, 0.15 g) was taken in a round bottom flask containing 45 ml of chloroform and subsequently, catalytic amount of TFA (1 drop) was added into it. The solution was followed by the slow addition of (1*R*, 2*R*)-1,2-diamino cyclohexane (**3**) (0.5 mmol, 0.057 g), solubilized in 15 ml of CHCl₃. Thereafter, the reaction mixture was allowed to stir for 5 days at RT, under N₂ atmosphere. After 5 days, the reaction mixture was filtered and concentrated into 10 ml by slow nitrogen flow. After that, the reaction mixture was precipitated by adding hexane into it. The precipitate was then filtered off, re-dissolved in dichloromethane. Again, the dichloromethane solution was concentrated by nitrogen flow and re-precipitated with hexane, filtered off to give the barrel **1** as a white solid (0.15 g, 84%). It is also noteworthy that the nanobarrel **1**, composed of 12 imine bonds, is quite susceptible towards hydrolysis and does not survive under chromatographic purification.

¹H-NMR (1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane-*d*₂, 400 MHz, 298K) δ (ppm): 8.42 (s, 12H), 7.92 (s, 12H), 7.87 (d, *J* = 8.7 Hz, 12H), 7.63 (d, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 12H), 7.46 (d, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 12H), 7.32 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 12H), 3.02-3.08 (br. m, 12H), 1.81-1.90 (br. m, 48H), 1.26 (s, 54H).

¹³C-NMR (dichloromethane-*d*₂, 125 MHz, 298K) δ (ppm): 161.17, 149.12, 142.78, 137.80, 135.42, 132.06, 131.07, 128.32, 128.05, 122.67, 78.02, 35.79, 34.05, 33.73, 31.91, 30.27, 25.95, 25.72, 25.30

MS MALDI (m/z): 2769.337. Calculated for [M+Ag]⁺ C₁₉₂H₁₈₆N₁₂Ag: 2769.408.

Figure S12. ^1H -NMR spectrum of **1** (1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane- d_2 , 400 MHz, 298K). Asterisks indicate solvent residual peaks.

Figure S13. ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of **1** (dichloromethane- d_2 , 125 MHz, 298K). Asterisks indicate solvent residual peaks.

Synthesis of C₆₀@1.

Barrel **1** (0.02 mmol, 0.053 g) was stirred in the presence of an excess of C₆₀ (3 equiv) in dichloromethane or chloroform (5 mL) for overnight at RT, under the N₂ atmosphere. Thereafter, the solution was filtered and the solvent was removed from the filtrate by slow nitrogen flow. The solid was then re-dissolved in dichloromethane (1 mL) and poured into hexane in order to obtain the precipitate, which was collected by centrifugation to give desired host-guest complex C₆₀@**1** as a dark brownish solid (0.06 g, 89%).

¹H-NMR (1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane-*d*₂, 400 MHz, 298K) δ (ppm): 8.40 (s, 12H), 7.93 (s, 12H), 7.91 – 7.85 (m, 12H), 7.64 – 7.56 (m, 12H), 7.52 – 7.43 (m, 12H), 7.33 – 7.26 (m, 12H), 3.08 (br. s, 12H), 1.73-1.92 (br. m, 48H), 1.26 (br. s, 54H).

¹³C-NMR (dichloromethane-*d*₂, 125 MHz, 298K) δ (ppm): 161.01, 149.18, 142.74, 141.32, 137.83, 135.46, 132.06, 131.05, 128.19, 128.12, 122.68, 78.37, 36.05, 34.29, 33.73, 32.05, 31.88, 26.05, 25.76, 25.34

MS MALDI (m/z): 3490.434. Calculated for [M+Ag]⁺ C₂₅₂H₁₈₆N₁₂Ag: 3490.129.

Figure S14. ^1H -NMR spectrum of $\text{C}_{60}\text{@1}$ (1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane- d_2 , 400 MHz, 298K). Asterisks indicate solvent residual peaks.

Figure S15. ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of $\text{C}_{60}\text{@1}$ (dichloromethane- d_2 , 125 MHz, 298K). Asterisks indicate solvent residual peaks.

References

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